

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT CIRIL

SPOKE N 3 – CULTURAL-INDUSTRY REGENERATION IMMERSIVE LAB

DELIVERABLE D 3.1: Context related analysis of lesser known cultural areas

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from (April 2023) to (March 2024)
Periodic report date and version:	03/04/2024 version 1
Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D3.1	Context related analysis of lesser known cultural areas	R	PU	12	30/03/2024			03/04/2024
D3.2	Technological mock-up for personalised itineraries	R	PU	18				
D3.3	Methodology and training contents based on immersive technologies approach	R	PU	24				
D3.4	SHERIL Pilot	DEM	PU	32				

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art and Point of Interests (POI)	R	10	04/02/2024	.		04/04/2024
M2	Main user domain and user content defined		14	18/03/2024			

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

The Deliverable D1 entitled "Context related analysis of lesser-known cultural areas" is started at the beginning of April 2023.

During this period are achieved completely the Milestone M1 titled "Analysis of the state of art and Point of Interests (POI)". The Deliverable investigated about how visitor attendance in lesser-known cultural areas can be increased through the adoption of ICT, as well as at implementing new technological architectures that allow, the construction of thematic and customised routes, improving the planning capacity of cultural sites through innovative data collection and analysis tools.

1.2 Context

The Research Team is composed by Professor Gerardo Canfora, Rector of University del Sannio, Gaetano Natullo, Director of Department of Law, Economics, Management and Quantitative Methods (DEMM), Paolo Esposito, Angelo Riviezzo, Biagio Simonetti and Pasquale Vito.

During the 2023, two researchers were recruited and included in the Research Team: Piera Zerillo, Research Fellow, and Massimiliano Tufo, Ph.D. Student.

2. Methodology

To achieve the aim of the Project, two Literature reviews were conducted:

- Literature review on the theoretical framework;
- Literature review on public value developed in the frame of the project.

The activities implemented are manifold and consist of Literature Review (LR) that is a widely used methodology to provide an overview of a given field. The aim being to elucidate the characteristics of reviews and the main methodological steps involved in their planning, conduct, and publication, the scientific knowledge available in top international and Italian scientific Journals has been collected and synthesized.

Although LR applies a less rigorous approach than that required to conduct systematic reviews, it does not reflect a mere alternative to them, but pursues specific objectives with its own methods. LR are valuable when systematic reviews are not available (or possible) or when there is a need to summarize available articles on debated and articulated issues.

Possibly, literature reviews can also be considered as a "precursor" to systematic reviews in future.

3. Results

The research begins by analysing the legal framework and gathering information on the different types of policies already applied. After examining the theoretical framework on public value and social impact, it is crucial to comprehend how to create new public value.

Italy is esteemed for containing approximately 40% of the world's artistic heritage. According to a recent study (Banca IFIS, 2024), the Italian beauty ecosystem—comprised of its locations, stakeholders, and services—contributes 29,2% to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The analysis of lesser-known cultural areas in Italy, particularly focusing on internal regions, Campania, and Benevento, reveals a complex interplay of historical, economic, and demographic factors. Italy's internal areas, defined by their distance from essential service centers, cover about 58.8% of the national territory and include 3,851 municipalities, which is 48.5% of all Italian municipalities. These areas face significant demographic challenges, with a population decline from 14 million to 13.3 million between 2002 and 2023, contrasting with a 9.1% growth in central areas.

The Italian government has implemented the National Strategy for Inner Areas (SNAI) to address these issues by enhancing accessibility, promoting cultural tourism, and supporting sustainable development. However, despite these efforts, internal areas continue to struggle economically. In 2022, the average annual per capita income in these regions was €17,405, which is 83.9% of the national average. Moreover, only 19.8% of local business units are located in internal areas, employing 17.2% of the national workforce.

In Campania, the situation is compounded by the region's fragmented economic structure and insufficient infrastructure. Campania is home to several UNESCO World Heritage sites, which could serve as anchors for regional development if managed effectively within a cohesive framework. For example, in Benevento there are the Traian's Arch and Saint Sofia Church. However, the lack of coordination among stakeholders and inadequate investment in infrastructure hinders the full exploitation of these cultural assets for economic growth.

Statistically, the demographic decline in internal areas is exacerbated by factors such as aging populations and youth migration. Between 2014 and 2024, the population in these areas decreased by 5%, while central areas experienced a 1.4% decline. Furthermore, projections indicate that provinces with fewer residents in internal areas are likely to experience further depopulation by 2030. In Benevento, as in other internal areas, addressing these demographic and economic challenges requires a multifaceted approach that integrates cultural preservation with sustainable development strategies.

Benevento, an historic town in Campania, exemplifies the challenges faced by lesser-known cultural areas. Known for its historical significance and architectural heritage, Benevento has untapped potential for cultural tourism. However, it suffers from limited accessibility and inadequate promotion. The city's economic activities remain underdeveloped due to fragmented governance and insufficient investment in infrastructure.

4. Conclusion

To address these challenges effectively, research must begin by analyzing the legal framework and gathering information on the different types of policies already applied. This involves examining existing legislation and initiatives aimed at supporting cultural areas, such as the SNAI, to understand their strengths and weaknesses. Following this, it is essential to delve into the theoretical framework on public value and social impact. Understanding how public value is created and how it contributes to social impact is crucial for developing strategies that enhance the economic and cultural vitality of these regions.

Comprehending how to create new public value is particularly important in the context of lesser-known cultural areas. This involves identifying opportunities for innovation in governance, policy implementation, and community engagement. By fostering collaboration among stakeholders and leveraging cultural heritage, these areas can generate new public value that supports sustainable development and enhances local quality of life.

In conclusion, lesser-known cultural areas in Italy, particularly those in Campania and Benevento, face significant economic and demographic challenges. However, with strategic governance, investment in infrastructure, and promotion of cultural heritage, these regions can transform into vibrant centres of cultural tourism while preserving their historical identity. A crucial issue that emerged is the use of innovative technologies to mitigate overtourism and attract tourists to lesser-known cultural areas. However, their effectiveness depends on coordinated action among stakeholders to leverage cultural assets for sustainable economic growth. By integrating theoretical insights on public value and social impact into policy-making, these regions can unlock new opportunities for development and create lasting benefits for local communities.

5. Contribution of the Deliverable to NODES Objectives

Findings of the analysis, regarding public value creation and public value destruction, are part of 2 papers submitted in two International Scientific Conference. Currently, they are not yet publications but may become so in the future.

6. References

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